

Labour market and financial consequences of divorce and separation¹

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Abstract

Divorce and separation may have different consequences for the economic well-being of the former partners, depending on their resources, opportunities, constraints, and coping strategies. The most common outcome is the deterioration of financial circumstances, especially for women and mothers. However, the post-separation financial situation may also be improved by intensifying participation in the labour market. The main objective of the paper is to analyse how the financial and employment situation of women and men change after partnership dissolution in Hungary in the short and middle term.

We use data from the five longitudinal waves of the Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey (2001–2016/2017) and we look at change between pairs of consecutive waves. We focus on women and men who had lived with a spouse or partner in one survey wave and this relationship dissolved by the next wave. Only respondents aged below 60 are analysed. We use various measures of financial and employment situation and strategies that may help cope with income loss. We look at parents and non-parents, as well as divorce from marriage and separation from an unmarried union separately.

Results indicate that partnership dissolution in Hungary is associated primarily with deterioration in household-level economic wellbeing – especially among mothers –, while labour market adaptation, such as employment entry or increased working hours, appears more common among women than men. The findings also suggest that partnership dissolution may create opportunities for occupational advancement, but mainly for the childless.

Keywords: divorce, separation, financial situation, employment status, panel data, Generations and Gender Survey, Hungary

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Introduction

Partnership dissolution represents a major turning point in the life course that may fundamentally reshape individuals' labour market trajectories and economic circumstances. The end of a union often creates financial strain and uncertainty, forcing former partners to adapt to the loss of shared resources, the reorganization of care responsibilities, and changed living arrangements. At the same time, separation or divorce may also open up new opportunities and strategies, such as increased labour market participation, greater economic independence, or the renegotiation of work and family roles. Consequently, partnership dissolution can be understood both as a constraint and as a process of adaptation to new social and economic conditions. In this paper, we examine how the labour market position and economic wellbeing of women and men change following partnership dissolution in Hungary.

This study contributes to the literature on the economic consequences of partnership dissolution in several ways. First, while previous research has focused primarily on women, we examine post-dissolution labour market and economic changes for both women and men, allowing for a direct comparison of gendered adaptation patterns. Second, we distinguish between divorce and the dissolution of unmarried cohabitation, which is particularly relevant in the Hungarian context, where cohabitation became increasingly widespread during the study period and differs substantially from marriage in terms of stability and economic integration. Third, we compare parents and non-parents, thereby highlighting how caregiving responsibilities and family obligations shape post-separation economic vulnerability and labour market responses. In addition, instead of relying on a single indicator, we analyse multiple dimensions of economic wellbeing, including employment, personal and household income, poverty risks, and subjective financial hardship. Finally, the analyses are based on rich five-wave longitudinal survey data with a large sample size, making it possible to follow individuals across partnership transitions and examine changes in their labour market and economic situation over time. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. First, we review the theoretical and empirical literature on the labour market and economic consequences of partnership dissolution, with particular attention to gender differences and parenthood. Next, we present the Hungarian institutional and labour market context, focusing on family policy arrangements, gendered employment patterns, and the spread of cohabitation. The subsequent section describes the data, sample selection, variables, and analytical strategy. We then present the empirical results in four parts: entry to and exit from employment, labour market adaptation, changes in individual income, and changes in household-level economic wellbeing. Finally, we summarize the main findings, discuss their implications, and suggest directions for future research.

Background

Partnership dissolution and economic adaptation

Divorce and separation may have important consequences for the labour market position and economic wellbeing of former partners. The dissolution of a marriage or cohabiting union means that former partners lose the economies of scale associated with a shared household, as certain costs – particularly housing and everyday living expenses – can no longer be divided between two adults. As a result of the sudden change in household composition and income structure, partnership dissolution is often associated with worsening financial circumstances and increased poverty risks (Burkhauser

& Duncan, 1989; Cherlin, 1992; Mortelmans, 2020). At the same time, the socioeconomic consequences of separation also depend on former partners' labour market resources, employment stability, human capital, and their ability to compensate for income loss through labour market adaptation.

A fundamental theoretical framework for understanding the economic consequences of union dissolution is Becker's (1981, 1985) New Home Economics model. According to this approach, couples specialize within partnerships to maximize efficiency: men focus primarily on market work and women on domestic labour and childcare. As a result, partnership dissolution affects men and women asymmetrically. Women may face economic disadvantages because their relationship-specific investments and care responsibilities weaken their labour market position, while men may experience disruptions related to the loss of household support. At the same time, dissolution can also increase women's labour market participation, as previously more dependent partners need to strengthen their own earnings.

Although the Beckerian model offers an elegant explanation for post-divorce gender disparities, modern family and labour sociology has highlighted several of its structural limitations. First, the model overlooks unequal bargaining power within households and the long-term economic dependency and vulnerability that specialization inflicts upon women (Oppenheimer, 1997). Second, the theory is difficult to reconcile with the Central and Eastern European context, specifically Hungary, where the dual-earner family model has been the institutionalized norm since the era of state-socialist modernization (Blossfeld & Drobnič, 2001; Dupcsik & Tóth, 2015). In Hungary, the majority of women do not withdraw from the labour market entirely; rather, they combine paid employment with the vast majority of unpaid domestic and care work, often described as women's "second shift" (Hochschild & Machung, 2012). Consequently, post-dissolution gender inequalities reflect not only economic dependence, but also unequal care responsibilities, differences in employment stability, and the loss of household economies of scale.

Previous research has consistently shown that women are more likely than men to experience worsening financial circumstances after divorce and separation (e.g. Bayaz-Ozturk et al., 2018; Burkhauser & Duncan, 1991; Cherlin, 1992; Mortelmans, 2020). The main reasons include women's weaker labour market attachment and their greater likelihood of retaining child custody after separation. At the same time, several studies found that women may partially compensate for post-separation economic losses by intensifying their labour market participation, for example by entering employment, increasing working hours, or changing jobs (Bayaz-Ozturk et al., 2018; Poortman, 2000; Tamborini et al., 2015). Results from the United States also indicate that child support and support from personal networks may mitigate some of the negative economic consequences of separation among mothers (Tach & Eads, 2015). Leopold (2018), analysing German data, found that men were more vulnerable to the short-term subjective consequences of divorce, while the most persistent gender differences emerged in women's household income losses and poverty risks.

Parenthood may further intensify post-dissolution inequalities. Following separation, custodial parents – most often mothers – face a paradoxical situation. They have greater economic needs due to childrearing responsibilities, while their caregiving obligations constrain their labour market opportunities and time resources (Poortman, 2000). Consequently, single parenthood is frequently associated with elevated poverty risks and financial hardship. In contrast, non-custodial parents, most often fathers, may face weaker day-to-day caregiving burdens, although separation can still negatively affect their economic wellbeing, social integration, and subjective wellbeing.

Finally, the economic consequences of union dissolution may also differ between marriage and cohabitation. Cohabiting unions are generally characterized by lower levels of legal and economic

integration, less extensive income pooling, and fewer joint investments than marriages (Evans & Gray, 2021; Hiekel et al., 2014). Therefore, the dissolution of cohabiting unions may result in less severe economic disruption than divorce. However, previous research suggests that as cohabitation becomes increasingly widespread and institutionalized, the economic consequences of separation among cohabiting parents may increasingly resemble those observed after divorce (Tach & Eads, 2015).

The Hungarian context: institutional framework, labour market, and family dynamics

To analyse the economic and labour market consequences of union dissolution in Hungary between 2001 and 2017, several country-specific institutional and structural factors must be considered.

Rooted in the state socialist legacy, Hungary has long been characterised by a dual-earner family model (Bukodi, 2005). At the same time, gender inequalities within families remained substantial. The domestic division of labour remained highly traditional, with women performing the overwhelming majority of domestic and childcare work, while social expectations for men to act as primary breadwinners remained strong (Spéder, 2011). In addition, a persistent gender wage gap meant women's earnings were consistently lower than men's.

The Hungarian welfare system also strongly shapes post-dissolution adaptation. Hungary's "familialistic" welfare regime (Hobson et al., 2011) provides a combination of insurance-based and universal childcare benefits that allow mothers to remain at home with children until age three (Makay, 2020). Consequently, employment rates among mothers with young children are relatively low (Blaskó, 2011; Ökrös & Makay, 2024). If partnership dissolution occurs during this early childrearing phase, women may face particularly high economic vulnerability.

Post-separation maternal adaptation is further constrained by the structure of the Hungarian labour market. During the study period, the share of part-time employment was among the lowest in the European Union (Hárs, 2012). Due to low wages and institutional disincentives, part-time employment often did not provide sufficient income for independent living. Consequently, separated mothers frequently faced strong pressure to return to full-time employment despite substantial caregiving responsibilities.

The financial vulnerability of custodial single mothers is reinforced by the characteristics of the Hungarian child support system (Szalma & Rékai, 2019). Court-ordered child support payments were often low and difficult to enforce, while state advances remained strongly means-tested. At the same time, shared physical custody was relatively rare, with children most often remaining with mothers after separation. As a result, the economic burden of post-separation childcare was borne disproportionately by women.

Partnership dissolution in Hungary is also strongly stratified by social background. Földházi (2019) showed that lower educational attainment and weaker labour market integration are associated both with a higher risk of union dissolution and with more disadvantaged post-separation trajectories. The study also highlighted the importance of repartnering: individuals who entered a new partnership after separation generally experienced more favourable economic and social outcomes than those remaining single.

Another important contextual factor is the rapid spread of cohabitation during the study period. Between 2001 and 2016, cohabitation increasingly functioned as a precursor to marriage, a long-term alternative to marriage, as well as a long-preferred arrangement after divorce or widowhood (Murinkó, 2023; Spéder, 2005). In spite of their popularity, cohabiting unions in Hungary are substantially less stable than marriages (Murinkó, 2019; Makay & Murinkó, 2021), while cohabiting

partners are generally less economically integrated and less likely to pool income or accumulate joint property (Präg et al., 2019). Therefore, the dissolution of cohabiting unions may have different economic consequences than divorce.

Previous Hungarian research has also pointed to the vulnerability of divorced fathers. Vukovich (2006) found that divorced fathers, especially those living without a new partner, had weaker labour market attachment, more frequent unemployment experience, lower household income, and higher poverty risks than fathers living in intact unions. Divorced fathers living alone were also more likely to experience social isolation, weaker support networks, and poorer subjective wellbeing, highlighting that partnership dissolution may negatively affect men's social and economic integration as well.

Research aims and expectations

The main objective of the paper is to analyse how the financial and employment situation of women and men change after partnership dissolution in Hungary. We concentrate on changes within no more than three–four years after divorce or separation, i.e. short- and medium-term changes. We use various measures of financial and employment situation and strategies that may help cope with the income loss. We look at divorce from marriage and separation from an unmarried union separately, and we also differentiate between parents and non-parents. The number of hypotheses reflect the relatively high number of outcome variables used in the analysis.

Our research questions are the following:

1. How does partnership dissolution affect labour market participation and economic wellbeing in Hungary?
2. Do these consequences differ between women and men?
3. Do parents and non-parents experience different post-dissolution trajectories?
4. Are the consequences of divorce and cohabitation dissolution different?

Based on previous research and the Hungarian institutional context, we expect women – especially mothers – to face greater deterioration in household-level economic wellbeing following partnership dissolution than men. At the same time, women may respond to income loss by strengthening their labour market participation and increasing their earnings. In contrast, men's labour market attachment is expected to remain more stable, although some men may experience employment instability and social disadvantage following separation. We also expect the economic consequences of cohabitation dissolution to be less severe than those of divorce due to lower levels of economic integration within cohabiting unions.

Data and methods

Data and analytical sample

We use data from the five longitudinal waves of the Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey (GGS), conducted between 2001 and 2016/2017 (Makay et al., 2025; Murinkó & Spéder, 2016; Vikat et al., 2007). The survey was designed to be nationally representative of the Hungarian resident population aged 18 and above. The main focus of this large panel survey was fertility, partnerships, and aging, as well as related opinions and attitudes. The GGS focuses on family dynamics and relationships, with rich information on employment, education, and family-related attitudes as background variables.

In Hungary, the first wave of the GGS was carried out in 2001 ($n = 16,363$), while the fifth wave took place at the turn of 2016 and 2017 ($n = 6,328$). In wave 4 (2012), the original sample was supplemented with a refreshment sample of respondents aged 18–49 ($n = 4,334$), whose members were also re-interviewed in wave 5. All five waves and both the original and the refreshment sample are included in the analysis.

The analysis focuses on changes between consecutive survey waves, as detailed information on respondents' employment and financial situation is only available at the time of the interviews not for the periods between waves. Consequently, the analytical sample includes only respondents who participated in at least two waves. Accordingly, the data are structured as person-period observations representing transitions between consecutive survey waves.

Only respondents below age 60 are included in the analysis. First, during the observation period many individuals had already retired by this age, which limited their ability to respond to the financial challenges of union dissolution through adjustments in employment. Second, above age 60, unions were increasingly dissolved by the death of a partner rather than by divorce or separation.

Key variable: partnership transitions

In the data set, detailed partnership histories are recorded for each respondent from age 16 onward, both retrospectively and prospectively, with monthly precision. Four types of partnership events are registered: the start and end of living with a partner, marriage, and the death of a partner. Thus, partnership status can be reconstructed not only at the time of each interview but for every month of the observation period.

We created a variable capturing changes in partnership status between consecutive survey waves (e.g. between t_1 and t_2). The variable is based on partnership status at both waves, the formation of a new union between waves, and the dissolution of unions through separation, divorce, or widowhood. It also takes into account whether these events occurred in the partnership that existed at t_1 or in a new relationship formed between t_1 and t_2 . All observed combinations are presented in *Table 1* and the distribution of the variable is shown in *Table 2*.

Table 1: Definition of the categories of the partnership transitions variable

<i>Partnership transitions between t_1 and t_2</i>	<i>Had a partner at t_1</i>	<i>If had a partner:</i>		<i>New union between t_1 & t_2</i>	<i>If new union: it dissolved by t_2</i>	<i>If dissolved: partner died</i>
		<i>union dissolved by t_2</i>	<i>partner died</i>			
Steady single	0	-	-	0	-	-
New relationship	0	-	-	1	0	-
New relationship & divorce/separation	0	-	-	1	1	0
New relationship & widowhood	0	-	-	1	1	1
Intact union	1	0	-	-	-	-
Divorce/separation (no repartnering)	1	1	0	0	-	-
Widowhood (no repartnering)	1	1	1	0	-	-
Divorce/separation & repartnering	1	1	0	1	0	-
Widowhood & repartnering	1	1	1	1	0	-

Source: authors' compilation.

In this paper, respondents are considered single if they do not have a spouse or cohabiting partner; thus, individuals in a LAT (living-apart-together) relationship are classified as single. Cohabiting couples who married between two survey waves are still treated as being in a continuous relationship with the same partner. As the dates of marriage are available in the data, it is possible to distinguish

between the dissolution of marital and non-marital unions. A union dissolution is classified as divorce if spouses ceased to live together in the same household or if they report being separated, regardless of the legal dissolution of the marriage.

Table 2: Partnership transitions between consecutive waves by sex

<i>Partnership transitions between t_1 and t_2</i>	<i>Women</i>		<i>Men</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Steady single	4 064	25.6	4 009	28.6	8 073	27.0
New relationship	1 086	8.0	995	8.6	2 081	8.3
New relationship & divorce/separation	112	1.0	108	1.0	220	1.0
New relationship & widowhood	1	0.0	0	0.0	1	0.0
Intact union	9 522	58.4	7 349	56.4	16 871	57.5
Divorce/separation (no repartnering)	664	4.5	479	4.0	1 143	4.2
<i>of which: divorce</i>	377	2.3	248	1.9	625	2.1
<i>separation</i>	287	2.2	231	2.1	518	2.1
Widowhood (no repartnering)	206	1.3	33	0.3	239	0.8
Divorce/separation & repartnering	173	1.2	145	1.1	318	1.2
Widowhood & repartnering	4	0.0	3	0.0	7	0.0
Total	15 626	100.0	13 088	100.0	28 714	100.0

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017); authors' calculations.

Notes: Percentages are weighted using longitudinal survey weights, while reported sample sizes are unweighted.

For the multivariate analyses, we use a simplified version of the partnership transition variable and restrict the sample to respondents who had a co-residential partner at t_1 , while also differentiating between the dissolution of married and unmarried unions (see *Table 3*). The main analytical group consists of respondents who experienced divorce ($n = 625$) or separation ($n = 518$) between two consecutive waves and did not enter a new partnership by t_2 . This group is compared with respondents who remained in a continuous relationship with the same partner throughout the observation period (intact union; $n = 16 871$). All other partnership trajectories, involving widowhood and/or repartnering after union dissolution, are grouped into a residual “other” category ($n = 564$) because of their relatively small number and their substantively different implications for employment and financial outcomes.

Table 3: Partnership transitions between consecutive waves among partnered respondents at t_1 , by sex (%)

	<i>Women</i>	<i>Men</i>	<i>Total</i>
Intact union	89.3	91.3	90.3
Divorce	3.5	3.1	3.3
Separation	3.3	3.3	3.3
Other partnership transitions	3.9	2.3	3.1
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), $n = 18,578$; authors' calculations, percentages weighted using longitudinal survey weights.

Outcome variables

Several outcome variables are used to capture changes in respondents' labour market position and economic wellbeing between consecutive survey waves.²

² Another important aspect of the material consequences of union dissolution – housing – has been examined in a previous article of one of the authors (Murinkó, 2019).

Labour market outcomes include employment status, working hours, occupational status, managerial position, and self-employment. *Employment status* distinguishes between employed respondents – including employees and the self-employed – and non-employed respondents, including students, old-age pensioners, disability pensioners, parents on childcare leave, unemployed persons, and homemakers.

Working hours refer either to the week preceding the interview or, if the respondent did not work during that week because of illness, holiday, or another type of leave, to a typical working week. The original continuous variable is recoded into three categories: less than 40 hours, exactly 40 hours, and more than 40 hours per week. The majority of the respondents indicated that they worked 40 hours, which is typical for full-time employment. Only 13% worked less than 40 hours (17% among women) and 32% worked more than 40 hours (40% among men).

Occupational status is measured using the International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI; Ganzeboom et al., 1992; Ganzeboom & Treiman, 2010), which assigns occupations a continuous status score based on their typical educational and income characteristics. ISEI scores were generated using the online conversion tools developed by Ganzeboom and Treiman (2019). Managerial position indicates whether the respondent supervises other employees or works in a managerial role. Self-employment distinguishes respondents working in their own business or independently from salaried employees.

Economic wellbeing is measured using several indicators capturing both individual and household-level financial conditions. *Individual monthly net income* includes earnings, social transfers, and other personal income sources. Analyses of individual income are restricted to respondents who were employed at both t_1 and t_2 and who had non-missing, non-zero income values. Both individual and equivalized household income are categorized into quintiles in order to analyse upward and downward income mobility between waves.

Equivalized monthly net household income includes the income of all household members and is adjusted for household size and composition. *Poverty status* is defined as living in a household with an equivalized income below 60% of the median equivalized household income.

Finally, *subjective household financial situation* captures perceived economic wellbeing. Respondents were asked: “What would you say, how do you manage with this income?” The five response categories ranged from severe financial hardship (“have to go without”, “have financial problems from month to month”) through a modest livelihood (“we can just make ends meet by budgeting carefully”) to financial comfort (“we live acceptably”, “we live without problems”). When looking at changes between waves, we grouped the two lowest categories together as “bad”, the two highest ones as “good”, and we called the middle category “acceptable”.

Control variables

All models include a common set of *socio-demographic controls* measured at t_1 : age group, ethnicity, parental status, settlement type, and the highest level of educational attainment of both the respondent and the (former) partner.

The parental status variable indicates whether the respondent has children.³ We do not control for post-separation living arrangements with children, as only 80 separated or divorced fathers in the sample live with their children. Because childcare responsibilities directly shape labour market

³ In this paper, “childless” refers to respondents who had no children at t_1 ; however, some of them may have become parents by the subsequent survey wave or later.

participation, the models predicting employment include more detailed controls for the age of the youngest child and childbirth between waves. For the remaining outcomes, a simpler indicator of parental status was considered sufficient.

All models control for the prior value of the dependent variable measured at t_1 , allowing us to estimate associations with changes in respondents' labour market and economic situation between consecutive waves. In addition, all models include survey wave controls to account for period-specific differences in the economic and social context.

Only pre-transition characteristics likely to confound both partnership transitions and subsequent labour market and economic outcomes were included as controls. Variables directly reflecting the economic organization of the couple were not controlled for, as these may constitute part of the mechanism linking partnership dissolution to later economic outcomes.

Methods

To examine the association between partnership transitions and subsequent employment and financial outcomes, both descriptive methods and regression models are used. We estimate a series of lagged dependent variable models in which the dependent variables are measured at t_2 , while controlling for their values at t_1 . Partnership transitions constitute the key independent variable, alongside including a set of socio-demographic characteristics measured at t_1 as controls. This modelling strategy approximates changes between consecutive survey waves while accounting for pre-existing differences between respondents. Because respondents can contribute multiple observations to the analyses, standard errors are clustered at the individual level. Since the relationship between partnership dissolution and labour-market adjustment is expected to differ substantially by gender, all analyses are conducted separately for women and men.

Depending on the measurement level of the outcome variable, linear, binary logistic, ordered logistic, or multinomial logistic regression models are estimated. To facilitate interpretation, the results are presented as adjusted predicted probabilities and predicted values calculated from the fitted models. All analyses use wave-specific longitudinal weights that adjust for sample attrition between survey waves.

The analyses identify associations between partnership transitions and subsequent labour market and financial outcomes, but they do not allow for strong causal conclusions. Although partnership changes are measured between two consecutive survey waves, the exact timing of changes in employment or financial conditions within the same interval is not observed. Consequently, it cannot be determined whether these changes occurred before or after union dissolution. Moreover, previous research suggests that individuals may adjust their labour market behaviour in anticipation of divorce or separation, implying that changes in employment may precede the actual dissolution of the union (e.g. Johnson & Skinner, 1986; Sen, 2000).

Findings

Employment entry and exit

Descriptive results indicate that women intensified their labour market participation after partnership dissolution: they tended to stay in or enter the labour market more often than women who lived in an intact relationship, particularly among mothers (*Table 4*). Approximately one-fifth of divorced women became active between t_1 and t_2 , compared with 13% of women in intact unions.

Among men, partnership dissolution was associated primarily with a higher probability of becoming inactive between waves. Around 15% of divorced or separated men became non-employed, compared with 8% of men who remained in an intact union. At the same time, roughly one in ten divorced or separated men entered employment between waves.

Among women who got divorced or separated and entered the labour market between survey waves, every second had been on maternity or parental leave at t_1 , while the largest group was the unemployed among men. Divorced or separated men who left the labour market most often became unemployed or disability pensioners (results not shown).

Table 4: Change in employment status by partnership transition, prior parental status, and sex (%)

Change in employment status	Partnership transition					If divorce or separation		
	Intact union	Divorce	Separation	Other	Total	No children	Child(ren)	Total
<i>Women</i>								
Stayed employed	52.2	60.7	51.8	52.1	52.5	71.2	52.4	56.4
Became non-employed	12.1	6.5	10.8	16.0	12.0	8.1	8.7	8.6
Became employed	12.9	20.1	18.8	13.2	13.3	13.3	21.2	19.5
Stayed non-employed	22.8	12.7	18.5	18.6	22.2	7.4	17.7	15.5
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
<i>Men</i>								
Stayed employed	75.9	67.4	66.8	69.8	75.2	73.1	64.6	67.1
Became non-employed	7.8	15.5	13.7	8.2	8.2	14.5	14.6	14.6
Became employed	6.7	7.5	11.5	10.5	7.0	10.6	9.2	9.6
Stayed non-employed	9.7	9.6	8.1	11.5	9.7	1.8	11.6	8.8
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 and lived with a partner at t_1 , $n = 18,578$; authors' calculations. All differences between groups are statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level (Chi² test).

The descriptive results also suggested that parenthood mattered primarily for women: divorced or separated mothers entered employment considerably more often than mothers in intact unions, whereas differences by parental status were much smaller among men. However, these differences largely disappeared after controlling for prior employment status, socio-demographic characteristics, and parental status in the regression models. This result suggests that the higher rate of labour market entry among divorced and separated mothers mainly reflects the return of previously inactive mothers — many of whom had been on maternity or parental leave — rather than a distinct effect of parenthood itself. (Separate regression analyses restricted to respondents with children produced substantively similar results and are therefore not shown.)

The regression results nevertheless confirmed distinct gendered patterns of labour market adaptation following partnership dissolution (*Figure 1*). Among women who had not been employed at t_1 , the predicted probability of being employed at t_2 was higher after divorce than among women who remained in intact unions. At the same time, women who had been employed at t_1 showed only a modest decline in employment stability following partnership dissolution.

For men, the regression results confirmed a different pattern. Men who had been employed at t_1 were less likely to remain employed after divorce or separation than men in intact unions. In contrast, among previously non-employed men, partnership dissolution was not associated with a substantially higher probability of entering employment. Overall, the findings suggest that partnership dissolution

tends to strengthen women’s labour market attachment, while among men it is associated mainly with a somewhat increased risk of labour market withdrawal.

Figure 1: Predicted probability of being employed at t_2 by partnership transition between t_1 and t_2 , prior employment status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 and lived with a partner at t_1 , $n = 18,578$. Predicted probabilities from logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, ethnicity, parental status, childbirth between waves, settlement type, and survey wave; authors’ calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Working conditions

Descriptive results related to the relationship between partnership transitions, parental status and changes in working conditions are presented in Table 5. Among respondents who were employed at both t_1 and t_2 , partnership dissolution was associated with moderate changes in working conditions, although the patterns differed by gender and parental status.

Table 5: Changes in working conditions by partnership transition, prior parental status, and sex

	Partnership transition					If divorce or separation		
	Intact union	Divorce	Separation	Other	Total	No children	Child(ren)	Total
<i>Women</i>								
<i>Working hours per week at t_1 and t_2 (%)</i>								
<40, <40	7.2	4.4	5.2	10.5	7.2	4.1	5.0	4.8
<40, 40	8.5	14.7	10.7	11.4	9.0	8.3	14.7	12.9
<40, 40+	3.1	6.6	5.5	3.7	3.3	5.0	6.5	6.1
40, <40	6.4	5.4	5.6	4.7	6.2	4.8	5.8	5.5
40, 40	40.5	28.9	29.2	34.2	39.5	24.3	30.8	29.0
40, 40+	10.9	12.2	12.0	6.2	10.8	12.1	12.1	12.1
40+, <40	3.2	3.8	4.0	3.0	3.2	5.8	3.1	3.8

	<i>Partnership transition</i>					<i>If divorce or separation</i>		
	<i>Intact union</i>	<i>Divorce</i>	<i>Separation</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>No children</i>	<i>Child(ren)</i>	<i>Total</i>
40+, 40	9.8	9.9	12.6	14.0	10.1	12.9	10.4	11.1
40+, 40+	10.4	14.1	15.3	12.3	10.8	22.8	11.6	14.6
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
<i>Change in working hours (%)</i>								
increase total	22.5	33.5	28.2	21.3	23.1	25.3	33.3	31.1
decrease total	19.3	19.1	22.1	21.7	19.5	23.5	19.3	20.4
<i>Managerial position at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
no - no	78.1	81.6	82.2	80.8	78.4	80.3	82.5	81.9
no - yes	7.8	7.8	10.9	9.1	8.0	12.8	7.9	9.2
yes - no	5.6	5.4	4.8	4.7	5.5	4.0	5.5	5.1
yes - yes	8.6	5.2	2.1	5.3	8.1	2.9	4.2	3.8
<i>Self-employment at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
no - no	88.9	90.5	88.7	89.3	88.9	87.2	90.6	89.7
no - yes	2.5	2.5	4.1	2.6	2.5	5.0	2.5	3.2
yes - no	2.3	1.4	4.6	0.4	2.3	3.5	2.5	2.8
yes - yes	6.4	5.7	2.7	7.6	6.3	4.3	4.4	4.3
<i>Mean change in ISEI scores</i>	0.157	0.300	0.342	-1.506	0.116	2.714	-0.305	0.318
<i>Change in ISEI scores (%)</i>								
decrease	26.2	24.8	33.2	38.5	26.7	22.4	30.4	28.4
no change	43.4	48.6	27.6	31.5	42.8	30.8	42.8	39.7
increase	30.4	26.6	39.1	30.0	30.5	46.8	26.8	31.9
<i>Men</i>								
<i>Working hours per week at t1 and t2</i>								
<40, <40	2.5	2.3	4.1	7.9	2.6	0.8	4.4	3.2
<40, 40	5.7	5.6	5.2	5.3	5.7	5.2	5.4	5.4
<40, 40+	4.0	1.4	4.8	9.1	4.0	3.9	2.8	3.2
40, <40	4.4	3.5	3.5	3.4	4.4	7.0	1.8	3.5
40, 40	26.5	21.9	25.8	21.0	26.3	27.4	22.3	24.0
40, 40+	14.2	20.6	16.2	9.1	14.4	18.3	18.3	18.3
40+, <40	3.5	3.6	4.7	4.6	3.5	6.3	3.2	4.2
40+, 40	15.5	17.3	13.8	11.4	15.4	11.9	17.2	15.5
40+, 40+	23.7	23.9	21.9	28.2	23.7	19.2	24.6	22.9
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
<i>Change in working hours (%)</i>								
increase total	23.9	27.5	26.2	23.5	24.1	27.4	26.6	26.8
decrease total	23.4	24.3	22.0	19.4	23.3	25.2	22.2	23.1
<i>Managerial position at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
no - no	70.2	70.0	76.8	67.9	70.3	69.5	75.4	73.5
no - yes	8.8	9.7	8.2	10.2	8.8	12.7	7.1	8.9
yes - no	7.1	6.9	5.8	5.1	7.0	8.4	5.3	6.3
yes - yes	13.9	13.5	9.2	16.8	13.8	9.4	12.2	11.3
<i>Self-employment at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
no - no	78.8	80.8	82.2	72.6	78.9	79.5	82.5	81.6
no - yes	4.1	4.9	4.3	7.1	4.2	6.9	3.6	4.6
yes - no	4.0	4.6	2.4	3.4	3.9	3.6	3.4	3.5
yes - yes	13.1	9.6	11.1	17.0	13.0	10.0	10.5	10.4
<i>Mean change in ISEI scores</i>	-0.591	-2.023	-0.937	-1.092	-0.646	-0.199	-2.025	-1.472
<i>Change in ISEI scores (%)</i>								
decrease	33.7	33.3	36.6	53.9	34.1	30.2	37.0	35.0
no change	39.6	42.4	30.6	18.0	39.1	32.8	37.8	36.3
increase	26.7	24.3	32.9	28.1	26.8	37.0	25.3	28.7

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t₁, and were continuously employed, n = 11,148; authors' calculations. Differences across partnership transition groups are statistically significant at the p<0.05 level only regarding working hours, managerial position among women and ISEI change for both sexes.

Women who experienced divorce or separation were more likely than women in intact unions to increase their weekly working hours between waves (they most often increased it to 40 hours per

week; Table 5). Roughly one-third of divorced mothers increased their working hours, compared with about one-quarter of divorced childless women and women living in intact unions. At the same time, divorced and separated childless women were also somewhat more likely to reduce their working hours, indicating substantial heterogeneity in post-dissolution labour market adaptation. Among men, partnership dissolution was also associated with increased working hours, even though the differences by partnership transition were modest. Divorced and separated fathers showed particularly high working hours.

The regression results show more modest patterns than the descriptive statistics, largely due to the wide confidence intervals (Figure 2). The findings suggest that changes in working hours after partnership dissolution reflect heterogeneous adaptation strategies rather than a general and uniform increase in labour supply. Nevertheless, some gender- and parenthood-specific patterns emerge. Among women, mothers were more likely to increase their working hours following divorce or separation than childless women, which is consistent with the assumption that post-dissolution income loss may stimulate labour market adaptation among women with children. However, the substantial overlap between confidence intervals suggests that these differences should be interpreted cautiously. Among men, the patterns are weaker and less consistent. Divorced men showed somewhat higher probabilities of increasing working hours than other groups, but the differences were relatively small and statistically uncertain. In the separation and “other” categories, the results do not indicate a clear tendency towards work intensification.

Figure 2: Predicted probability of increasing working hours from t_1 to t_2 by partnership transition, parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 who lived with a partner at t_1 and were continuously employed, $n = 11,148$. Predicted probabilities from logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, ethnicity, parental status, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Occupational mobility patterns, measured by changes in ISEI scores, showed limited evidence of systematic downward mobility among women following partnership dissolution (Table 5). Mean changes in ISEI scores were positive among divorced and separated women and somewhat higher than among women in intact unions, although mothers experienced slightly more frequent downward mobility than childless women after union dissolution. At the same time, childless divorced or separated women were relatively likely to experience upward occupational mobility.

Among men, mean changes in ISEI scores were negative across all partnership transition groups, with particularly strong declines among divorced men. Downward occupational mobility was more common among separated and divorced fathers than among childless men, while upward mobility was less frequent among fathers. These results suggest that partnership dissolution may be associated with some occupational disadvantage among men, especially among fathers.

Figure 3: Predicted probability of ISEI increase and decrease between t_1 and t_2 by partnership transition, parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 who lived with a partner at t_1 and were continuously employed, $n = 11,148$. Predicted probabilities from multinomial logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, ethnicity, parental status, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. The predicted probabilities of unchanged ISEI scores are not shown.

Most associations between partnership transitions and ISEI mobility visible in the descriptive analyses disappeared in the multivariate models (Figure 3). Regression results indicate little evidence of systematic occupational mobility among divorced and separated mothers and fathers. Among childless respondents, however, divorce was associated more frequently with upward occupational mobility. In contrast, men and childless women who repartnered or became widowed between consecutive survey waves were more likely to experience downward occupational mobility. Changes in managerial positions were relatively limited overall. Only childless divorced or separated respondents showed a somewhat higher-than-average probability of entering managerial positions (Table 5). The regression results (Figure 4) partly confirm this association, but only for divorced respondents. In contrast, separated childless respondents appeared less likely to become managers than individuals living in intact unions. However, these results should be interpreted cautiously given the wide confidence intervals around the estimated predicted probabilities.

Figure 4: Predicted probability of becoming a manager from t_1 to t_2 by partnership transition, parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 who lived with a partner at t_1 and were continuously employed, $n = 11,148$. Predicted probabilities from logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, ethnicity, parental status, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. The patterns were the same for both sexes.

Transitions into or out of self-employment were relatively rare overall: 86% of continuously active respondents (employees or self-employed persons) did not change their employment status between consecutive waves. Nevertheless, separated women and childless women experiencing partnership dissolution were somewhat more likely than other groups to move between salaried employment and self-employment (Table 5). However, the regression models did not identify any statistically significant association between partnership transitions and the probability of becoming self-employed.

Personal economic consequences

For respondents who were employed or self-employed at both t_1 and t_2 , their net personal income is compared between the two survey waves. Descriptive results suggest that partnership dissolution was not associated with substantial declines in personal income. On the contrary, both women and men who experienced divorce or separation had somewhat higher average personal incomes at t_2 than respondents who remained in intact unions (Table 6).

The distribution of income mobility also showed only limited evidence of downward mobility after partnership dissolution. Among women, divorced and separated respondents were slightly more likely to move upward in the personal income distribution than women in intact unions, while the proportion experiencing downward mobility differed little between groups. Among men, the patterns were more mixed: divorced men most often remained in the same income quintile, whereas separated men somewhat more frequently experienced downward mobility.

Differences by parental status among divorced and separated respondents were relatively modest. Childless women showed slightly higher rates of downward income mobility than mothers, while among men, fathers were somewhat more likely to remain in the same income quintile after partnership dissolution.

Regression models of personal income or movements between personal income quintiles showed no clear and consistent pattern of income change or mobility following partnership dissolution.

Table 6: Change in personal monthly net income by partnership transition, prior parental status, and sex

	Partnership transition					If divorce or separation		
	Intact union	Divorce	Separation	Other	Total	No children	Child(ren)	Total
<i>Women</i>								
Mean personal income (thousand HUF)	114.2	127.6	123.4	124.1	115.5	128.7	124.6	125.7
Change in personal income quintiles (%)								
remained in same quintile	49.7	46.3	44.9	44.2	49.2	44.0	46.2	45.6
moved to higher quintile	26.8	31.2	31.2	32.4	27.4	29.8	31.7	31.2
moved to lower quintile	23.5	22.5	24.0	23.4	23.4	26.2	22.1	23.2
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
<i>Men</i>								
Mean personal income (thousand HUF)	141.9	150.4	149.6	161.3	142.8	156.0	147.3	150.0
Change in personal income quintiles (%)								
remained in same quintile	52.6	61.2	46.5	44.2	52.5	48.0	55.9	53.4
moved to higher quintile	23.0	17.3	26.9	25.0	23.0	26.9	20.3	22.3
moved to lower quintile	24.4	21.6	26.6	30.8	24.6	25.1	23.8	24.2
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t_1 , were continuously employed, and had non-zero and non-missing income at both t_1 and t_2 , $n = 11,148$; authors' calculations. Differences across partnership transition groups are statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Household economic consequences

Descriptive results reveal a mixed pattern regarding the household-level economic consequences of partnership dissolution (Table 7). Mean equivalized household income among divorced women was slightly higher than among women living in intact unions, while separated women had substantially lower average household incomes. However, indicators capturing changes in household economic position point to considerably greater economic instability following partnership dissolution,

especially among women and parents. Around half of divorced or separated women moved to a lower household income quintile between waves, compared with only 27% of women in intact unions. Among men, downward mobility following partnership dissolution was less pronounced and the differences between partnership transition groups were substantially smaller. Divorced men experienced somewhat lower household incomes and somewhat more frequent downward mobility than men in intact unions, while the economic position of separated men differed less from continuously partnered men. Differences by parenthood status were less consistent for mean household income levels, although childless men experiencing partnership dissolution tended to have higher household incomes than fathers.

The regression results largely confirm these descriptive patterns. Predicted values from linear regression models show substantially lower household income levels among divorced and separated respondent than in intact unions, regardless of parental status (*Figure 5*). Multinomial logistic regression models predicting household income mobility also indicate that women experiencing partnership dissolution had a considerably higher probability of downward mobility and a lower probability of upward mobility than continuously partnered women (*Figure 6*). The associations between partnership dissolution and downward household income mobility were similar among men and women.

Table 7: Changes in household income measures by partnership transition, prior parental status, and sex

	Partnership transition					If divorce or separation		
	Intact union	Divorce	Separation	Other	Total	No children	Child(ren)	Total
<i>Women</i>								
<i>Mean equalized household income (thousand HUF)</i>	133.1	149.9	97.1	133.7	132.5	126.7	123.4	124.1
<i>Change in equalized household income quintiles (%)</i>								
remained in same quintile	42.9	30.6	27.5	29.4	41.5	26.9	29.7	29.1
moved to higher quintile	29.7	21.7	19.6	38.2	29.5	20.1	20.8	20.7
moved to lower quintile	27.4	47.7	52.9	32.4	29.1	53.0	49.5	50.3
<i>Poverty status at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
yes - yes	6.4	7.6	8.0	6.3	6.5	0.0	9.9	7.8
yes - no	7.2	6.6	6.9	11.2	7.4	3.1	7.7	6.7
no - yes	6.0	20.5	20.7	9.2	7.1	14.4	22.3	20.6
no - no	80.4	65.4	64.5	73.2	79.1	82.6	60.1	64.9
<i>Change in subjective household income (%)</i>								
consistently bad	7.1	14.4	12.2	11.1	7.7	3.5	15.9	13.3
bad but improving	10.3	11.5	14.9	15.0	10.7	13.8	12.9	13.1
consistently acceptable	26.0	18.5	20.4	20.5	25.3	19.6	19.4	19.4
acceptable but improving	13.1	7.7	8.8	15.5	12.9	13.2	6.9	8.2
acceptable but worsening	7.4	17.2	13.3	9.2	8.0	9.4	16.8	15.3
consistently good	24.0	13.2	12.5	16.3	22.9	18.6	11.4	12.9
good but worsening	12.2	17.6	18.0	12.6	12.6	21.9	16.7	17.8
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
<i>Men</i>								
<i>Mean equalized household income (thousand HUF)</i>	126.8	115.8	128.2	144.3	126.9	150.2	111.4	122.2
<i>Change in equalized household income quintiles (%)</i>								
remained in same quintile	42.5	33.3	44.0	49.5	42.5	38.2	39.1	38.8
moved to higher quintile	28.9	32.1	27.9	22.9	28.8	30.1	29.8	29.9
moved to lower quintile	28.6	34.6	28.1	27.7	28.8	31.7	31.1	31.3
<i>Poverty status at t1 and t2 (%)</i>								
yes - yes	7.3	8.3	11.6	12.4	7.6	3.9	12.3	10.0
yes - no	7.2	9.2	7.3	8.6	7.3	4.3	9.8	8.2
no - yes	7.3	14.0	10.0	7.3	7.6	7.9	13.5	11.9

	Partnership transition					If divorce or separation		
	Intact union	Divorce	Separation	Other	Total	No children	Child(ren)	Total
no - no	78.2	68.5	71.1	71.7	77.5	83.9	64.4	69.8
<i>Change in subjective household income (%)</i>								
consistently bad	8.4	12.3	13.2	14.6	8.8	7.0	15.1	12.8
bad but improving	11.0	12.4	8.9	13.4	11.0	6.5	12.3	10.6
consistently acceptable	26.1	23.0	19.2	21.1	25.6	20.0	21.4	21.0
acceptable but improving	13.2	15.2	16.5	11.2	13.3	18.5	14.8	15.9
acceptable but worsening	8.3	11.1	10.7	8.8	8.5	7.6	12.2	10.9
consistently good	21.1	9.4	20.4	20.5	20.7	28.0	9.9	15.1
good but worsening	12.0	16.7	11.0	10.4	12.1	12.4	14.3	13.8
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t_1 and had non-missing values on the income variable, $n = 17,624$; authors' calculations. Differences across partnership transition groups are statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Figure 5: Predicted log monthly net equalised household income at t_2 by partnership transition between t_1 and t_2 , prior parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t_1 , and had non-zero and non-missing household income at both t_1 and t_2 , $n = 17,624$. Predicted values from linear regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, working hours, ethnicity, parental status, childbirth between waves, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Figure 6: Predicted probability of change in monthly net equalised household income quintile by partnership transition between t_1 and t_2 , prior parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t_1 , and had non-zero and non-missing household income at both t_1 and t_2 , $n = 17,624$. Predicted values from multinomial logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, working hours, ethnicity, parental status, childbirth between waves, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Poverty risks also increased substantially following partnership dissolution, especially among mothers. According to the descriptive results, around one-fifth of divorced or separated mothers entered poverty between waves, compared with only 6% of women in intact unions (Table 7). Mothers experiencing partnership dissolution were also substantially less likely to remain consistently non-poor. Among men, increases in poverty risks were more moderate, although divorced and separated fathers also experienced elevated rates of entering poverty compared with continuously partnered men. Regression results again reinforce these patterns (Figure 7). Logistic regression models of poverty status – controlling for poverty status at t_1 – show a substantially higher probability of entering poverty among divorced and separated women than among women in intact unions. Among men, partnership dissolution was also associated with increased poverty risks, although the differences between partnership transition groups were smaller and confidence intervals wider than among women. The probability of entering poverty does not seem to differ by parental status.

Figure 7: Predicted probability of poverty status by partnership transition between t_1 and t_2 , prior parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60, lived with a partner at t_1 , and had non-zero and non-missing household income at both t_1 and t_2 , $n = 17,624$. Predicted probabilities from logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, working hours, ethnicity, parental status, childbirth between waves, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Descriptive analyses of subjective household financial situation point to substantial gender and parenthood inequalities following partnership dissolution (Table 7). Divorced and separated women, particularly mothers, were much more likely to report persistent or worsening financial hardship and substantially less likely to report consistently good financial conditions than women in intact unions. Among mothers experiencing partnership dissolution, around 46% reported either consistently bad or worsening financial circumstances. Childless women generally reported more favourable subjective financial trajectories than mothers. Among men, subjective financial deterioration following partnership dissolution was also visible, but the patterns were weaker and less polarized than among women. The regression models indicate that parents were more likely to experience severe financial hardship following partnership dissolution than respondents in intact unions (Figure 8). However, severe financial hardship was not concentrated exclusively among divorced mothers. Men also showed relatively high predicted probabilities of severe financial hardship, even exceeding those observed among childless women (Figure 8). In addition, men living in intact unions often reported higher predicted probabilities of severe hardship than women in intact unions.

Figure 8: Predicted probability of severe financial hardship by partnership transition between t_1 and t_2 , prior parental status, and sex

Source: Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey, waves 1–5 (2001–2017), respondents aged below 60 who lived with a partner at t_1 and had no missing values on subjective household income at both t_1 and t_2 ; $n = 12,095$. Predicted probabilities from ordinal logistic regression models controlling for activity status at t_1 , age group, education, working hours, ethnicity, parental status, childbirth between waves, settlement type, and survey wave; authors' calculations. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals.

Conclusions

The findings provide a nuanced picture of the labour market and financial consequences of partnership dissolution in Hungary and reveal substantial differences across outcome dimensions, gender, and parental status. Overall, the results suggest that partnership dissolution is associated less with a uniform economic decline than with heterogeneous adaptation processes combining labour market adjustment, household income loss, and subjective financial strain.

Regarding the first research question, the analyses show that partnership dissolution is associated with important changes both in labour market participation and household-level economic wellbeing, although the direction and magnitude of these changes differ across outcomes. Women who experienced divorce or separation were more likely than women in intact unions to enter employment or remain employed. At the same time, partnership dissolution among men was associated primarily with a somewhat higher probability of labour market withdrawal. Changes in working hours were generally moderate and heterogeneous, but divorced or separated women — particularly mothers — somewhat more often increased their working hours than women in intact unions. After union dissolution childless respondents were found to have higher probability of upwards occupational mobility and becoming managers than people in intact unions. In contrast, the analyses found little evidence of transitions into self-employment following partnership dissolution.

The results concerning personal and household income point in different directions. Partnership dissolution was not associated with substantial declines in personal income. In contrast, household-level economic indicators showed much clearer signs of deterioration.

Concerning gender differences, the findings only partly support expectations derived from earlier research and theoretical approaches. Women generally experienced more severe deterioration in household-level economic wellbeing following partnership dissolution than men, particularly regarding downward household income mobility and poverty risks. At the same time, women also appeared more likely to respond through labour market adaptation, especially by entering employment or increasing working hours, which may explain the modest average increase in their personal income. Men, by contrast, showed less evidence of labour market intensification and somewhat greater risks of becoming non-employed following divorce or separation. However, the analyses also indicate that men were not unaffected by partnership dissolution. In particular, subjective financial hardship among men was often comparable to — and in some cases even higher than — that observed among women.

The analyses by parental status produced more mixed results than initially expected. Parenthood mattered most clearly for labour market participation among women: mothers who experienced partnership dissolution more frequently entered employment or increased working hours than mothers living in intact unions. However, many of these differences weakened after controlling for prior employment status and socio-demographic characteristics, suggesting that the observed employment entry often reflected the return of previously inactive mothers from childcare leave rather than a distinct effect of parenthood itself. Parenthood was also associated with somewhat higher poverty risks and more negative subjective financial evaluations after partnership dissolution, particularly among women, although these differences were less systematic in the multivariate models than expected. The findings on upward occupational mobility and entry into managerial positions among childless respondents suggest that partnership dissolution may represent not only a source of economic strain but also an opportunity for occupational advancement; however, such opportunities appear to be far more accessible to individuals without childcare responsibilities.

The comparison between divorce and the dissolution of cohabiting unions also yielded relatively modest differences. Although descriptive statistics sometimes suggested slightly more severe household-level economic deterioration after separation from cohabitation than after divorce, the overall patterns were broadly similar across the two types of union dissolution. This finding is consistent with earlier arguments that, as cohabitation becomes increasingly widespread and institutionalized, its economic consequences may increasingly resemble those of divorce, especially among parents.

Taken together, the findings partly support the theoretical expectations outlined at the beginning of the paper. The results are broadly consistent with Beckerian arguments and subsequent research emphasizing the asymmetric economic consequences of partnership dissolution for women and men. Women's increased labour market participation following separation supports the idea that partnership dissolution may stimulate compensatory labour supply responses among women. At the same time, the findings also demonstrate the limitations of a strict specialization model in the Hungarian context. The absence of strong and systematic occupational downgrading among women, together with the relatively modest changes in personal income, suggests that most women had already maintained some labour market attachment before separation. This pattern reflects the long-standing dual-earner model characteristic of Hungary and the broader Central and Eastern European region.

The results also align with theoretical perspectives emphasizing the importance of care responsibilities and the loss of household economies of scale. The deterioration in household-level economic

wellbeing despite relatively stable or improving personal income suggests that the main economic consequences of partnership dissolution arise not primarily from the collapse of individual earnings, but from the transition from a shared household economy to separate households. This mechanism appears especially important in Hungary, where housing and living costs represent substantial burdens and where institutional support for single parents remains relatively limited. The findings concerning mothers' increased labour market participation together with elevated poverty risks further illustrate the tension between caregiving obligations and economic necessity described in earlier research.

Finally, the analyses highlight the substantial heterogeneity of post-dissolution trajectories. Partnership dissolution did not uniformly lead to economic decline or labour market instability. Some respondents experienced marked deterioration in household income and subjective wellbeing, while others showed relatively stable trajectories or signs of successful labour market adaptation. This heterogeneity suggests that the economic consequences of partnership dissolution cannot be understood through a single mechanism or outcome dimension alone, but rather reflect diverse adaptation strategies shaped by gender, parental status, prior labour market position, and household circumstances. As a continuation of this research, we plan to explore the existence of distinct post-dissolution adaptation types using latent class analysis, combining information on labour-market trajectories, changes in household income and poverty status, and subjective financial wellbeing. Such an approach may help identify typical adaptation strategies and reveal further gender differences in responses to partnership dissolution.

As a continuation of this research, we also plan to examine longer-term trajectories by following respondents across three consecutive survey waves. This approach would make it possible to analyse whether labour market and income changes observed between t_1 and t_2 persist, intensify, or reverse by t_3 , depending on subsequent partnership trajectories such as repartnering or continued singlehood. Analysing longer sequences of events may also contribute to a better understanding of the temporal ordering of partnership and economic changes and thereby provide more insight into potential causal mechanisms.

Several limitations of the study should be acknowledged. First, the panel design does not allow the precise timing of labour market, income, and partnership changes between survey waves to be identified. Consequently, it cannot be determined whether employment or income changes occurred before or after partnership dissolution, and some observed adjustments may reflect anticipatory behaviour preceding separation. Second, the data contain no direct information on job changes, such as changing employer, occupation, or sector, limiting our ability to identify the mechanisms underlying labour market adaptation. Third, some analytically important subgroups — particularly separated fathers living with children or respondents experiencing rarer partnership transitions — remain relatively small, resulting in wide confidence intervals and limiting statistical precision. Fourth, although the models control for a broad set of pre-transition socio-demographic characteristics and prior outcome values, the analyses remain observational and do not permit strong causal conclusions. Finally, the study focuses primarily on short- and medium-term changes between consecutive survey waves; longer-term adaptation trajectories following partnership dissolution may differ substantially from the patterns observed here.

References

- Bayaz-Ozturk, G., Burkhauser, R. V., Couch, K. A., & Hauser, R. (2018). The effects of union dissolution on the economic resources of men and women: A comparative analysis of Germany and the United States, 1985–2013. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 680(1), 235–258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716218793608>
- Becker, G. S. (1981). *A treatise on the family*. Harvard University Press.
- Becker, G. S. (1985). Human capital, effort, and the sexual division of labor. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 3(1, Part 2), S33–S58.
- Blaskó, Zs. (2011). Három évig a gyermek mellett – de nem minden áron: A közvélemény a kisgyermekes anyák munkába állásáról [Stay at home for three years – but not at all costs: Social values on maternal employment in Hungary]. *Demográfia*, 54(1), 23–44.
- Blossfeld, H. P., & Drobnič, S. (Eds.). (2001). *Careers of couples in contemporary societies: From male breadwinner to dual-earner families*. Oxford University Press.
- Bukodi, E. (2005). Női munkavállalás és munkaidő-felhasználás [Female employment and work time use]. In I. Nagy, T. Pongrácz, & I. Gy. Tóth (Eds.), *Szerepváltozások. Jelentés a nők és férfiak helyzetéről, 2005* (pp. 15–43). TÁRKI & Ifjúsági, Családügyi, Szociális és Esélyegyenlőségi Minisztérium.
- Burkhauser, R. V. & Duncan, G. J. (1989). Economic Risk of Gender Roles: Income Loss and Life Events over the Life Course. *Social Science Quarterly*, 70(1), 3–23.
- Cherlin, A. J. (1992). *Mariage, Divorce, Remarriage*. Harvard University Press.
- Dupcsik, Cs. & Tóth, O. (2015). Family systems and family values in twenty-first-century Hungary. In *Family and social change in socialist and post-socialist societies* (pp. 210–249). Brill.
- Evans, A., & Gray, E. (2021). Cross-national differences in income pooling among married and cohabiting couples. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 83(2), 534–550. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12721>
- Földházi E. (2019): *Hun házasodunk hun meg elvélünk: Párkapcsolatok megszűnése és új kapcsolatok kialakulása* [Sometimes we marry, sometimes we divorce: Partnership dissolution and repartnering]. L'Harmattan.
- Ganzeboom, H. B. G., de Graaf, P. M., & Treiman, D. J. (1992). A standard international socio-economic index of occupational status. *Social Science Research*, 21(1), 1–56.
- Ganzeboom, H. B. G. & Treiman, D. J. (2010). Occupational Status Measures for the New International Standard Classification of Occupations ISCO-08; with a Discussion of the New Classification. <http://www.harryganzeboom.nl/isol/isol2010c2-ganzeboom.pdf>
- Ganzeboom, H. B. G. & Treiman, D. J. (2019). International Stratification and Mobility File: Conversion Tools. <http://www.harryganzeboom.nl/ismf/index.htm>
- Hárs, Á. (2012). *Atipikus foglalkoztatási formák Magyarországon a kilencvenes és a kétezres években* [Atypical employment in the 1990s and 2000s in Hungary]. Budapest Working Papers on the Labour Market, No. BWP - 2012/7. Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Institute of Economics, Centre for Economic and Regional Studies.
- Hiekel, N., Liefbroer, A. C., & Poortman, A. R. (2014). Income pooling strategies among cohabiting and married couples: A comparative perspective. *Demographic Research*, 30, 1527–1560. <https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2014.30.55>
- Hobson, B., Fahlén, S., & Takács, J. (2011). Tensions in aspirations, agency and capabilities to achieve a work family balance: A comparison of Sweden and Hungary. *Social Politics*, 18(2), 168–198. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxr007>
- Hochschild, A., & Machung, A. (2012). *The second shift: Working families and the revolution at home*. Penguin.
- Johnson, W. R., & Skinner, J. (1986). Labor supply and marital separation. *The American Economic Review*, 76(3), 455–469.
- Leopold, T. (2018). Gender differences in the consequences of divorce: A study of multiple outcomes. *Demography*, 55(3), 769–797. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-018-0667-6>
- Makay, Zs. (2020). The family support system and female employment. In J. Monostori, P. Óri, & Zs. Spéder (Eds.), *Demographic Portrait of Hungary 2018* (pp. 85–105). Hungarian Demographic Research Institute.
- Makay, Zs., Kapitány, B., Monostori, J., Murinkó, L., & Spéder, Zs. (2025): *User guide for the five waves of the Turning Points of the Life Course Panel Survey (the Hungarian Generations and Gender Survey), 2001–2017* (Working Papers on Population, Family and Welfare No. 42). Hungarian Demographic Research Institute. <https://doi.org/10.21543/WP.2025.42>

- Makay, Zs. & Murinkó, L. (2021). Válás, élettársi kapcsolatok felbomlása [Divorce, dissolution of unmarried cohabitation]. In J. Monostori, P. Óri, & Zs. Spéder (Eds.), *Demográfiai portré 2021* (pp. 29–43). KSH Népeségtudományi Kutatóintézet.
- Mortelmans, D. (2020). Economic consequences of divorce: A review. In M. Kreyenfeld & H. Trappe (Eds.), *Parental life courses after separation and divorce in Europe* (pp. 23–41). Springer
- Murinkó, L. (2019). Housing consequences of divorce and separation in a 'super home ownership' regime: The case of Hungary. *Demographic Research*, 40(34), 975–1014.
<https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2019.40.34>
- Murinkó, L. (2023). The different faces of cohabiting unions in the new millennium. *Demográfia English Edition*, 66(5), 71–105. <https://doi.org/10.21543/DEE.2023.3>
- Murinkó, L. & Spéder, Zs. (Eds.). (2016). *Felhasználói kézikönyv az Életünk fordulópontjai panelkutatás 1–4. hullámához* [Users' guide for waves 1–4 of the Turning Points of the Life Course Panel Survey] (KSH NKI Kutatási jelentések, 97). KSH Népeségtudományi Kutatóintézet.
- Oppenheimer, V. K. (1997). Women's employment and the gain to marriage: The specialization and trading model. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 23(1), 431–453.
- Ökrös, F., & Makay, Zs. (2024). Mothers' labour market entry after childbirth: The role of pre-pregnancy job characteristics and socio-demographic factors. *Demográfia*, 67(2), 101–143.
<https://doi.org/10.21543/DEM.67.2.1>
- Poortman, A.-R. (2000). Sex differences in the economic consequences of separation: A panel study of the Netherlands. *European Sociological Review*, 16(4), 367–383. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/16.4.367>
- Präg, P., Begall, K., & Treas, J. (2026). Understanding the marriage–cohabitation gap in income pooling: Evidence from 29 European countries. *SocArXiv*. https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/rqzj3_v2
- Sen, B. (2000). How important is anticipation of divorce in married women's labor supply decisions? An inter-cohort comparison using NLS data. *Economic Letters*, 67(2), 209–216. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1765\(99\)00259-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1765(99)00259-1)
- Spéder, Zs. (2005). Az élettársi kapcsolat térhódítása Magyarországon és néhány szempont a demográfiai átalakulás értelmezéséhez [The rise of cohabitation as first union and some neglected factors of recent demographic developments in Hungary]. *Demográfia*, 48(2–3), 187–217.
- Spéder Zs. (2011): Ellentmondó elvárások között... Családi férfiszerepek, apaképek a mai Magyarországon. In I. Nagy & T. Pongrácz (Eds.), *Szerepváltozások: Jelentés a nők és férfiak helyzetéről 2011* (pp. 207–228). TÁRKI & Nemzeti Erőforrás Minisztérium.
- Szalma, I. & Rékai K. (2019). Szülői felügyeleti jog, kapcsolattartás és tartásdíjfizetés a különélő magyar szülők gyakorlatában [Child custody, visitation, and child support in the practice of non-resident Hungarian parents]. *Szociológiai Szemle*, 29(4), 83–114. <https://doi.org/10.51624/SzocSzemle.2019.4.4>
- Tach, L. M., & Eads, A. (2015). Trends in the economic consequences of marital and cohabitation dissolution in the United States. *Demography*, 52(2), 401–432. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-015-0374-5>
- Tamborini, C. R., Couch, K. A., & Reznik, G. L. (2015). Long-term impact of divorce on women's earnings across multiple divorce windows: A life course perspective. *Advances in Life Course Research*, 26, 44–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.alcr.2015.06.001>
- Vikat, A., Spéder, Zs., Beets, G., Billari, F. C., Bühler, Ch., Désesquelles, A., Fokkema, T., Hoem, J. M., MacDonald, A., Neyer, G., Pailhé, A., Pinnelli, A., & Solaz, A. (2007). Generations and Gender Survey (GGS): Towards a better understanding of relationships and processes in the life course. *Demographic Research*, 17(14), 389–440. <https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2007.17.14>
- Vukovich, G. (2006). Az elvált apák helyzetének néhány aspektusa [Some aspects of the circumstances of divorced fathers]. In T. Kolosi, I. Gy. Tóth, & Gy. Vukovich (Eds.), *Társadalmi riport 2006* (pp. 267–283). TÁRKI.